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Organoinsecticide Synergists. Part-I. Synthesis of Substituted-benzyl-2-propynyl Ethers and their Synergistic Activity

B. KRISHNA MOORTHY³

Department of Chemistry, Graduate School of Arts and Sciences, Fordham University, New York-10458

Manuscript received 8 June 1990, accepted 12 October 1990

A number of ring substituted benzyl 2-propynyl ethers (**3a-1**) were synthesised and tested for synergistic activity with mobam and supracide insecticides against house flies. The structures of synergist candidates were confirmed on the basis of elemental analysis, ir and nmr studies.

In the field of pesticide chemistry, a number of publications and dissertations have dealt with the synergistic activity of compounds containing the acetylenic group¹⁻³. Gibbons reported² that certain benzyl 2-propynyl ethers were effective as carbamate and organo phosphorous synergists. But very little work has been done on the structure-activity relationships of benzyl 2-propynyl ethers. In the present investigation, we have, therefore, carried out the synthesis of a large number of hitherto unreported benzyl 2-propynyl ethers and studied their synergistic activity. The synthetic steps involved to prepare ring substituted benzyl 2-propynyl ethers are outlined in Scheme 1. The benzyl bromides

(**2**) were prepared by heating appropriately substituted-toluenes either with NBS in the presence of light and benzyl peroxide as a catalyst or with bromine in carbon tetrachloride in the presence of light. The benzyl 2-propynyl ethers (**3a-1**) were prepared⁴ by the reaction of the appropriate benzyl bromides (**2**) with sodium propargylate in propargyl alcohol. Their structures were determined by ir and nmr spectral data. The compounds (**3a-1**) were screened for their synergistic activity with supracide or mobam against resistant female house flies, employing the Topical Application method⁶.

Biological activity: The results reveal that the presence of NO₂, CN and Br groups in *ortho*-position of the phenyl ring of compounds **3** enhanced the activity whereas substitution with acetyl, methyl and t-butyl groups resulted low activity. Dichloro derivatives appeared to be more active than the monochloro derivatives. Bromo derivatives were found to be good synergists for supracide. The most active candidates (100% 24 h mortality with supracide insecticide) were the 2,6-dichloro, 2-chloro-6-fluoro, 2-chloro-6-nitro, 2-chloro-6-cyano and 2-nitro-6-methyl derivatives.

Experimental

¹H Nmr spectra (CDCl₃) were determined on a Varian A-60A (60 MHz) spectrometer using TMS as an internal standard and ir spectra (CCl₄) on a Perkin-Elmer 137 spectrophotometer. Melting points were determined on a Fischer-Johns apparatus and are uncorrected. Elemental analysis were performed at Schwarzkopf Microanalytical Laboratory, Woodside, New York, U.S.A.

General method for preparation of benzylbromides (2). *Method A: Preparation of 2a-j:* To a solution of appropriately substituted toluene (0.1 mol) in carbon tetrachloride (150 ml) were added *N*-bromosuccinimide (19.6 g, 0.11 mol) and benzoylperoxide (1g) as a catalyst. The reaction mixture was stirred well and during the reaction two 150W lamps were focussed upon the reaction flask, which caused the reaction mixture to reflux. After completion of the reaction, as shown by rising of the formed succinimide to the top of the solution, the reaction mixture was cooled and filtered. The filtrate was first washed with 10% sodium bisulphite solution (100 ml), then with water, dried and concentrated under reduced pressure. The residue (if oily liquid) was either (if liquid) fractionally distilled at reduced pressure or crystallised (if solid) from suitable solvent.

Method B: Preparation of 2k-1: To a solution of appropriately substituted toluene (0.1 mol) in carbon tetrachloride (300 ml), bromine (19.2 g, 0.12 mol) was added slowly over a period of 6 h. The reaction mixture was further refluxed until the evolution of HBr gas eventually stopped. It was then cooled, washed with 10% sodium bisulphite solution (100 ml), then with water, dried and concentrated under reduced pressure. The crude residue

Scheme 1

*Present address: Pool Officer, Department of Studies in Chemistry, University of Mysore, Manasagangotri, Mysore-570 006

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL AND SPECTRAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS (3a-1)*

Compd. no.	Substituent Z	Yield %	M.p. b.p. (mm/Hg) °C	$\nu_{\max}$ cm ⁻¹	δ
3a	2-CN	68	93-94/0.1	3 289 ($\equiv$ CH), 2 222 (C $\equiv$ N), 2 110 (C $\equiv$ C), 1 082 (C-O)	7.58 (4H, m, ArH), 4.75 (2H, s, ArCH ₂), 4.28 (2H, d, J 2Hz, CH ₂ C $\equiv$ C), 2.45 (1H, t, J 2Hz, C $\equiv$ CH)
b	3-CN	88	94-95/0.1	3 311 ($\equiv$ CH), 2 222 (C $\equiv$ N), 2 128 (C $\equiv$ C), 1 087 (C-O)	7.55 (4H, m, ArH), 4.60 (2H, s, ArCH ₂), 4.20 (2H, d, J 2Hz, CH ₂ C $\equiv$ C), 2.43 (1H, t, J 2Hz, C $\equiv$ CH)
c	4-CN	78	62-63	3 247 ($\equiv$ CH), 2 212 (C $\equiv$ N), 2 101 (C $\equiv$ C), 1 111 (C-O)	7.7 (2H, d, J 9Hz, ArH), 7.47 (2H, d, J 9Hz, ArH), 4.63 (2H, s, ArCH ₂), 4.20 (2H, d, J 2Hz, CH ₂ C $\equiv$ C), 2.40 (1H, t, J 2Hz, C $\equiv$ CH)
d	2-Br	67	78-80/0.1	3 300 ($\equiv$ CH), 2 119 (C $\equiv$ C), 1 094 (C-O)	7.93 (4H, m, ArH), 4.60 (2H, s, ArCH ₂), 4.22 (2H, d, J 2Hz, CH ₂ C $\equiv$ C), 2.37 (1H, t, J 2Hz, C $\equiv$ CH)
e	4-Br	80	85-88/0.1	3 289 ($\equiv$ CH), 2 110 (C $\equiv$ C), 1 081 (C-O)	7.47 (2H, d, J 8Hz, ArH), 7.17 (2H, d, J 8Hz, ArH), 4.50 (2H, s, ArCH ₂), 4.10 (2H, d, J 2Hz, CH ₂ C $\equiv$ C), 2.37 (1H, t, J 2Hz, C $\equiv$ CH)
f	4-COCH ₃	80	107-09/0.05	3 279 ($\equiv$ CH), 2 119 (C $\equiv$ C), 1 667 (Conjug. C=O), 1 075 (C-O)	7.87 (2H, d, J 8Hz, ArH), 7.37 (2H, d, J 8Hz, ArH), 4.58 (2H, s, ArCH ₂), 4.13 (2H, d, J 2Hz, CH ₂ C $\equiv$ C), 2.47 (1H, t, J 2Hz, C $\equiv$ C-H), 2.47 (3H, s, COCH ₃)
g	4-(C(CH ₃) ₃)	85	86-88/0.08	3 289 ($\equiv$ CH), 2 110 (C $\equiv$ C), 1 355 (CH ₃), 1 082 (C-O)	7.27 (4H, s, ArH), 4.52 (2H, s, ArCH ₂), 4.07 (2H, d, J 2Hz, CH ₂ C $\equiv$ C), 2.30 (1H, t, J 2Hz, C $\equiv$ C-H), 1.30 (9H, s, C(CH ₃) ₃)
h	2-NO ₂ - 4-C(CH ₃) ₃	76	80-82/0.1	3 333 ($\equiv$ CH), 2 128 (C $\equiv$ C), 1 573, 1 310 (NO ₂), 1 087 (C-O)	8.02 (1H, s, ArH), 7.63 (2H, s, ArH), 4.88 (2H, s, ArCH ₂), 4.25 (2H, d, J 2Hz, CH ₂ C $\equiv$ C), 2.47 (1H, t, J 2Hz, C $\equiv$ CH), 1.35 (9H, s, (CH ₃) ₃ C)
i	2-NO ₂ - 3-CH ₃	81	96-97/0.1	3 300 ($\equiv$ CH), 2 114 (C $\equiv$ C), 1 529, 1 362 (NO ₂), 1 094 (C-O)	7.38 (3H, m, ArH), 4.62 (2H, s, ArCH ₂), 4.18 (2H, d, J 2Hz, CH ₂ C $\equiv$ C), 2.35 (1H, t, J 2Hz, C $\equiv$ CH), 2.35 (3H, s, CH ₃)
j	2-NO ₂ - 6-CH ₃	98	115-16/0.5	3 247 ($\equiv$ CH), 2 092 (C $\equiv$ C), 1 515, 1 337 (NO ₂), 1 078 (C-O)	7.57 (3H, m, ArH), 4.63 (2H, s, ArCH ₂), 4.22 (2H, d, J 2Hz, CH ₂ C $\equiv$ C), 2.42 (3H, s, CH ₃), 2.40 (1H, t, J 2Hz, C $\equiv$ CH)
k	2-Cl	76	35-36	3 425 ($\equiv$ CH), 2 232 (C $\equiv$ N), 2 128 (C $\equiv$ C), 1 550, 1 333 (NO ₂), 1 081 (C-O)	7.53 (3H, m, ArH), 4.80 (2H, s, ArCH ₂), 4.28 (2H, d, J 2Hz, CH ₂ C $\equiv$ C), 2.50 (1H, t, J 2Hz, C $\equiv$ CH)
l	2,6-Cl ₂	80	124-25/0.25	3 185 ($\equiv$ CH), 2 088 (C $\equiv$ C), 1 088 (C-O)	7.20 (3H, m, ArH), 4.77 (2H, s, ArCH ₂), 4.19 (2H, d, J 2Hz, CH ₂ C $\equiv$ C), 2.40 (1H, t, J 2Hz, C $\equiv$ CH)

*All compounds gave satisfactory elemental analyses; compounds 3m-r were prepared by reported method⁴.

was crystallised from a suitable solvent to yield pure benzyl bromides.

General method for preparation of benzyl 2-propynyl ethers (3a-1): The general procedure of Guermant⁴

was slightly modified and then used to prepare the title compounds. A solution of sodium metal (0.25 g, 0.0012 mol) in propargyl alcohol (50 ml) was added to a stirred solution of appropriate benzyl bromide (0.01 ml) in propargyl alcohol (50 ml) at 60°. The reaction mixture was then heated on a water-bath at 60–80° for about 4 h, then cooled to room temperature and neutralised with 5% hydrochloric acid and filtered. The propargyl alcohol in the filtrate was removed on a rotary evaporator. The residue left was treated with water and the oily layer was extracted into ether. The ether layer was separated, washed with water, dried and concentrated under reduced pressure. The crude residue was distilled fractionally at reduced pressure. The data are given in Table 1.

Evaluation of synergistic activity by Topical Application method⁶: Synergistic activity of the benzyl 2-propynyl ethers (3a–r) was determined with mobam and supracide insecticides against resistant female house flies of the Rutgers A-strain. The required number of house flies were chilled or anaesthetised with carbon dioxide and a solution of the test compound and insecticide (1 : 5) was prepared in appropriate concentrations. One microliter of the solutions containing the appropriate dose was applied to the dorsal region of the flies with the help of an automatic syringe dispenser. The flies were then held in plastic petridishes and cotton soaked in milk was provided. Tests were performed in triplicate using ten flies per test. The percent mortality after 24 h of the three sets of flies was averaged.

Acknowledgement

The author is grateful to Geigy Agricultural Chemical Co., New York and Fordham University, New York, U.S.A., for their financial support and to Dr. A. J. Forgash of Rutgers University, for conducting the biological tests.

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Synthesis of some 2-(2'-Methoxybenzoyl)-coumaran-3-ones

A. K. D. MAZUMDAR, P. K. KARMAKAR,
K. RANGACHARI, K. P. BANERJEE and K. D. BANERJI*

Chemical Laboratory, Marwari College,
Bhagalpur University, Bhagalpur-812 007

Manuscript received 2 March 1990, accepted 12 October 1990

IN continuation of our investigation¹ on coumaran-3-ones, we report here the synthesis of some 2-(2'-methoxybenzoyl)coumaran-3-ones. These coumaran-3-ones have been obtained by two routes. In the first route (Scheme 1) the 2-hydroxyacetophenones (1a–e) were condensed at low temperature (0–5°) with *o*-methoxybenzoic acid in pyridine with phosphorus oxychloride as a condensing agent, to give the corresponding benzoyloxyacetophenones (2a–e) in 70–90% yield. These esters on bromination with copper(II) bromide in dry dioxan afforded the ω -bromoacetophenones (3a–e) which on refluxing with KOH in dioxan gave the desired coumaran-3-ones, obviously through the unstable products (4)². Yield at all stages were excellent.

Scheme 1

Scheme 2 was designed not only to give a second route but *inter alia* afford a verification of the contention of Wadodkar and Daifode³, that the 3-bromochromones undergo ring contraction on refluxing with KOH, and produce the related